

Building Strong Character through Citizenship Education: Nurturing Responsible and Engaged Students

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ABSTRACT: The strategy of Character education is in rebuilding national identity and mobilizing Z generation the of social environment. These research objectives are to know citizenship education on strengthen student characters and how it works citizenship education learning in strengthening student characters. The research employed a descriptive qualitative method on Huberman and Miles theory (2002) with reduction, display and conclusion. The results show that the characters have performed that indicates the students with citizenship education can be a good effort for learners and the effort depth reflections the moral sequences it must be followed up with real actions so that they become practical and reflective. It takes several times to make all of those habits and the character of human form or person's behavior. There are some aspects in Educational characters to become a good behavior human beings are in their family and household, educational institutions, and society. The main step must be taken all of the correlation what they are in citizenship education almost finished between the three educational circles. Forming a characteristic and educational character will never succeed in our alive during there are not correlation each other onto harmony and continuity among educational circles appearing what in this reality whereas forming the characters of quality students are strong influencing in an environment such as family at home, school, and society.

KEYWORDS: Citizenship Education, Strengthen, Student Characters.

INTRODUCTION

Citizenship learning is intended to instill a sense of the homeland, increase the spirit of nationality, and form a national character that matches the philosophy, thinking of life, outlook on life, and the basis of the country is Pancasila (The basis of the state and ideology of Indonesia which is the basis for the development and life of the nation and state). Character is a characteristic of humans who can distinguish one from another. It may give a role and function to human behavior (Kandler et al., 2014). Forming the character is processed without any stop gained by education, life experience, and their circles. Branson (1999, p. 51) character can be described into two, namely public and private characters. It is important to consider the independence of citizens who have responsibility, self-respect, and dignity will make a good person and intelligent citizen. The efforts are in shaping the character of citizens what in through the development of education, both within the family, campus, and community. Tirtarahardja and La Sulo (2005, p. 1) intends to help students to develop their human potentials, the educating aims can be done properly and correctly if educators have a clear picture of who humans are. Humans have a characteristic called human nature. Human nature will form a map of human characteristics so that educational goals can be achieved. As a good personality, social and ethical people', in another part, the educational functions can be seen as a process of preparing citizens which are defined as a planned activity to provisioning students become good citizens (Pradana et al., 2020).

Planting character values can be integrated into the process learning to teach in each subject. The material taught includes elements related to norms or values in each subject which are then developed, made explicit, associated with the context of everyday life (Haniah et al., 2020; Ariani et al., 2022). Furthermore, learning character values is not only at the cognitive level, but touches on internalization, and real practice in the daily lives of students in society (Hidayati et al., 2020; Hamuddin et al., 2022; Hasnia et al., 2022).

In understanding what the students are needed in civic education learning activities as well as in the family life atmosphere namely in terms of providing tranquility and respect for rights and obligations as well as respect for their dignity, expected to be able to develop student characters in anticipating situations, and current conditions (Nurgiansah & Al Muchtar, 2018; Rahman, 2018).

Subjects that have great responsibility in building character, including the character of democracy and student tolerance.

Citizenship Education is moral and compulsory education given at every level of education from elementary school to university (Nuryadi, 2020). Supposedly, the substance of the material taught in Citizenship Education material is able to build the character of students. However, so far these subjects or courses have not been able to build the character of students. So, it is undeniable that today's youth are still experiencing a character crisis. So the researcher wants to describe how the Citizenship Education learning works in strengthening student characters, because this really needs more attention by the community to invite it to improve the current generation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Character Education

In the world of education, two terms are almost the same informing and also often used, namely pedagogics. Pedagogy has a meaning "education", in a pedagogic means "educational science". In terms that can come from Greek. It words having a meaning to association with children (Benner, 2023; Friesen, 2020).

Djumransjah in Carter V. Good's book Educational Philosophy as a social process that can be affected as individuals. Education determines one's way of life because the modification in one's view is also caused by interaction influences between intelligence, attention, experience, and so on. This understanding is almost the same as what Thompson said about education is an influence surrounding the individuals to produce permanent changes in their habitual behavior, thoughts, and attitudes (Carter, 2017; Thompson, 2018).

Educational philosophers state in formulating the meaning of education depends on viewpoint of humans; nature, characteristics, and the aim of human life itself (Vygotsky, 2020). The meaning of education in the philosophical literal of philosophy is human thinking on educational problems to solve and develop new theories based on normative, speculative, rational empirical, philosophical, and historical-philosophical thinking while education in the practical sense is a process of transferring or transforming knowledge or developing the potentials of students to achieve optimal development, as well as civilizing humans through the transformation of primary values (Spring, 2012).

Brubacher, in his book Modern Philosophies of Education, states: "Education is the organized development and equipping of all human, moral, intellectual, and physical powers, by and for their individual and social use, directed at the union of these activities. with its creator as final and". Meaning: education is an organized development and completeness of all human potential, moral, intellectual, and physical, by and for the individual personality and the use of society, which is directed to collect all these activities for the ultimate goal of life.

Character education has begun to be discussed at that time. Lickona is considered to be the bearer of it through his stunning work, *The Return of Character Education*, a book that awakens the Western world specifically where her lives, and the whole world of education in general, that character education is a must (2012). This is the beginning of the revival of character education. It can be shown every human has a certain character but not yet been perfected. In a simple meaning, character education can be anything positive that teacher does and affects the character students (Misnawati & Pranoto, 2022; Gould & Lewontin, 2020). A conscious and an earnest effort from a teacher while teaching the values to his students. Character education becomes an educational movement that supports the social development, emotional development, and ethical development of students (Saputro & Murdiono, 2020; Anam et al., 2019). It is a proactive effort by both schools and the government to help students developing the core of ethical values and performance values, such as caring, honesty, diligence, fairness, tenacity, responsibility, and self-respect.

B. Home Circle

Home is cored in family the pillar of the state with the family can be state rising or house. It is in a school where children study. They can learn noble qualities, such as loyalty, mercy, and compassion (Mulder & Lauster, 2010; Sokip et al., 2019). From family life, a father and husband acquire and cultivate the nature of courage and tenacity of attitude and effort in defending his relatives and making them happy during his life and after his death. The smallest unit is called as family what can be a proponent and spirit of the birth of a nation and society (Popenoe, 2020). On the other hand, it can also contribute to the collapse of a nation and society. It is not wrong to say that the family is the pillar of the state with the family can be state rising or house. Family has an important role in determining the progress of a nation, so they theorize that the family is a very important unit in society so that if the families which are the foundation of society are weak, society will be a weakness. Therefore, it believes various social

problems, such as rampant sexual crime and acts of violence, and all kinds of depravity in society are the result of weak family institutions (Ristroph & Murray, 2010).

C. Citizenship Education

One of the missions carried out by Civics is as character education. The linkage of Citizenship Education to character development was put forward by Cogan (1998, p. 13) who stated that Citizenship Education is the contribution or impact of education to the development of the characteristics that characterize a citizen. Therefore, to achieve citizens with character, the scope of formal education is needed. On the other hand, the same contribution was also conveyed by Djahiri (2002, p. 90) in his statement that in fostering the characteristics of these citizens, educational engineering is needed by referring to the philosophy of the state and making schools a laboratory of democratic citizenship.

D. Character

Understanding of what the real meaning of the character is not everyone has the same understanding, so that many interpretations arise on the meaning of character. Character is a combination of all human traits that are permanent, so that it becomes a special sign to distinguish one person with others (Dewantara, 2013). Character is often equated with what is called temperament which gives it an understanding that emphasizes psycho-social elements associated with education and the context in society, besides that character is also sometimes understood from a behavioral perspective emphasizing somatopsychic elements that individuals have from birth (Inkeles, 2017; Althof & Berkowitz, 2006). In this case the term character is considered the same as personality. Personality is considered as a characteristic or characteristic or style or characteristic of a person that comes from influences received from society, for example family in childhood, and also innate in a person from birth (Koesoema, 2010).

METHODOLOGY

The research used a descriptive qualitative method on Huberman's theory with reduction, display and conclusion. As an ex post facto type of this research can be shown the researcher does not give special treatment to the research subject. The information collected information based some experiences the parenting styles as experienced by students even though characters seeing in behavior shown carrying out tasks as general.

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

In citizenship learning education, the activities as the teacher integrating personality values that matched the subject has been finished it to be fulfilled before entering the classes. Collaboration Lecturer with students and students with their parents must be perfect and their home environment. Lecturers bring out closing activities as well, and this subject is constructive for the management of personalized learning for students.

A. Behavior on Strengthen Student Characters

The results of this study, the family at home can be very important to build the character on human beings as the researcher has a significant contribution to a person's character. Shown the influence in forming the existing characters and become the character basis.

Democratic citizens or socio-civic behavior is a necessity and need by every nation-state, which is carried out continuously, either through the formal education tract, informal, or out-of-school education. This program labeled them with various labels according to the philosophy and targets of the nation's expectations. Based on these expectations, there are several choices regarding strategies learning and methods, media choices, and evaluation patterns. These learning components are recently demanded professional efforts by their organization so that the citizenship education classes and schools as laboratories for democratic citizenship. The main message in citizenship education learning as a democracy laboratory cannot be separated from value education, because there is no science that can be giving value free. The meaning of value education is an education considering the objects from a moral and non-moral view, which includes aesthetics, namely giving the value of objects from the beauty of viewpoint and personal desire and ethics, namely giving the correct value or incorrect in interpersonal relationships. Civic virtues deserved to be developed to build an optimal civic culture. The core of the high-value virtues possessed on civic virtue brought by students before learning can be providing a value for strengthening the character when it gets a place and is directed to be better.

Character building for students in Indonesia can be done by creating learning that allows students to dare to express opinions, have curiosity, have an honest attitude towards themselves and others, and be able to maintain personal and environmental hygiene. Furthermore, in strengthening student character education, students need to be directed based on their level of development, for example by giving an example first by the teacher through the process of daily habituation. Apart from that, with the civics subject, this can be achieved because this subject includes the things that are called.

B. Citizenship Education on Strengthen Student Characters

The essence of this citizenship education on strengthen is to be able to educate students and parents by optimizing the various abilities and wisdom of parents towards their children in an intelligent way. Indicated they must have a good educational background, social knowledge, and religion so that they can transform all into children behaviors.

Conceptually, a citizen having five attributes can be seen into his book (Cogan, 1998, p. 2-3), namely: "...a sense of identity; the enjoyment of certain rights; the fulfillment of corresponding obligations; a degree of interest and involvement in public affairs; and an acceptance of basic societal values" identity; freedom to enjoy certain rights; fulfillment of related obligations; level of interest and involvement in public affairs; and the possession of basic social values.

Cogan (1998, p. 11) states these things can only be achieved if schools and all elements in society simultaneously work synergistically. In other words, citizenship education in the future cannot be seen and treated only as an ordinary subject in school but it should become an educational activity that is comprehensive in content and handling. Citizenship education as Political Education and General Education provides collaborative solutions between schools, families, and lecturers. Create meaningful of education with the aim of developing the educational citizens to have the characteristics as citizens.

Learning principles used in development Character education strives for students to know and accept the values of the nation's character as their own and responsible for the decisions taken through the stages recognize choices, assess choices, determine stance and then make a value in accordance with self-confidence.

CONCLUSION

Moral values as respect and responsibility can be formed a strong citizen character, especially if the teacher carries out the learning process professionally, and makes him/herself a model in the formation of citizen character. However, parental guidance must have an impact on the child's personality where parents should foster directly and indirectly in education at home, school, and in the community. The essence of this interventional education is the ability to educate families by optimizing the various abilities and wisdom of parents towards their children in an intelligent way. This indicates that parents must have a good educational background, social knowledge, and religion so that they can transform it into their children. Placing parents and the community as partners in value education by supporting the role of parents as the first moral teacher, encouraging parents and the community to support school activities, and utilizing institutions in the community to strengthen student characters as valuable educational in schools. In the end, the character of young citizens can be formed from the collaboration of the Civics learning process and parents where the school becomes the facilitator for the formation of this collaboration.

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